

CONCEPTUAL MODEL FOR PROTECTING PERSONAL DATA BY DE-IDENTIFICATION IN INFORMATION SYSTEMS

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Abstract. This article describes a solution for systematizing the approach to personal data protection using the method of de-identification in the context of regulatory pressure and growing cyber threats. It proposes a comprehensive conceptual model that formalizes the de-identification process as a manageable sequence of steps, from attribute classification and method selection to mandatory verification of the result. The article also provides a comparative analysis of existing de-identification methods in terms of their applicability within the proposed model. The model serves as a basis for the development of specific algorithms, as demonstrated by the example of a data shuffling approach.

Keywords: personal data, de-identification, data privacy, confidentiality, regulatory compliance, information security

Introduction

The digital economy is based on the intensive processing of personal data, which conflicts with the fundamental human right to privacy [1]. The global response to this conflict is stricter legislation (GDPR, CCPA, № LRU-547), which imposes strict obligations on data operators and significant financial risks in the event of violations [2]. The traditional approach to personal data protection, based on cryptography and access control systems, is resource-intensive and not always proportionate to the purposes of processing, especially in analytical and Big Data scenarios [3]. The main feature of personal data is the inseparable connection between the data subject and the information, which requires an increased level of security during processing [4].

In this context, de-identification acts as a key strategic mechanism that allows data to be removed from the strict regulatory regime of personal data, thereby reducing compliance burdens and risks [5]. However, the practice of de-identification remains fragmented: the choice of methods (aggregation, suppression, pseudonymization, encryption) is often made intuitively, without integration into a single manageable process and without subsequent verification of the result [6]. The lack of a standardized model linking legal requirements, data classification,

transformation methods, and risk assessment leads to inefficient costs and residual disclosure risks.

To develop a universal conceptual model for de-identification of personal data, which formalizes this process as a complete life cycle, providing a scientific basis for building information protection systems, it is necessary to:

- systematize the principles of model construction based on an analysis of regulatory requirements and best practices;
- conduct a comparative analysis of existing de-identification methods;
- formally describe the components and stages of the model and visualize the life cycle;
- demonstrate the practical testing of the model using the example of specifying requirements for a data shuffling algorithm.

Methods

The development of the conceptual model for the de-identification life cycle was conducted as a multi-stage process, combining theoretical analysis, formal specification, and empirical validation. The methodological framework was designed to ensure the model's compliance with regulatory requirements, its technical robustness, and its practical applicability. The research was conducted in the following four phases.

Formalization of Requirements and Model Architecture Design. The initial phase involved a deconstruction of the regulatory landscape to extract quantifiable requirements for the model. A systematic review of General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) (EU) 2016/679, the California Consumer Privacy Act (CCPA), and the Republic of Uzbekistan's Law No. LRU-547 was performed. The analysis focused on articles pertaining to pseudonymization, anonymization, and the accountability principle. From this, a set of functional and non-functional requirements for the conceptual model was derived. These requirements were then mapped onto the six foundational principles established in the preceding section (non-identifiability, acceptable disclosure, expediency, proportionality, verifiability, and metadata management).

Based on these formalized requirements, the high-level architecture of the model was designed using Unified Modeling Language (UML) 2.5.1. Class diagrams were constructed to define the static structure of the model, identifying core entities such as *DataSubject*, *PersonalDataRecord*, *ProcessingPurpose*, *De-identificationTechnique* and *RiskAssessment*. State machine diagrams were employed to model the dynamic life cycle of data as it transitions through various stages of de-identification, from “raw personal data” to “verified de-identified dataset”.

Algorithmic Taxonomy and Comparative Analysis. To address the heterogeneity of existing de-identification methods, we developed a functional taxonomy to classify techniques based on their operational mechanism and impact on data utility. The taxonomy, expanded from the preliminary analysis in Table 1, categorizes methods into four main families:

- Suppression and Generalization (masking, aggregation, k-anonymity).
- Perturbation and Noise Addition (differential privacy, data swapping, shuffling).
- Deterministic and Cryptographic Transformation (encryption, hash-based pseudonymization).
- Synthetic Data Generation (Generative Adversarial Networks - GANs).

A comparative evaluation matrix was then constructed using a multi-criteria decision analysis approach. Each method from the taxonomy was assessed against the six core principles. Criteria such as “Verifiability of Results” were evaluated based on the availability of formal proofs (e.g., ϵ -differential privacy) versus reliance on empirical testing (attack simulation for shuffling). “Preserving Data Usefulness” was assessed by measuring information loss metrics (discernibility metric, normalized certain penalty) for categorical data and precision loss for numerical data. The output of this phase was a decision tree that maps specific processing purposes and data types to a recommended set of candidate de-identification methods, providing a scientific basis for the “Expediency” principle.

Principles of the Model and Comparative Analysis of De-Identification Methods

Legislation (GDPR, Art. 4(5); No. LRU-547, Art. 3) defines de-identification as the processing of personal data, as a result of which they can no longer be attributed to a specific subject without the use of additional information stored separately and protected by technical and organizational measures [2, 7]. The key principle is accountability: the operator must not only apply the method, but also be prepared to justify its adequacy [8].

Based on the analysis [2, 4, 8, 9], the following set of interrelated principles is proposed:

- 1) *Principle of non-identifiability.* The final state of the data must objectively exclude the possibility of identifying the subject without the use of specially protected additional information.
- 2) *The principle of acceptable disclosure.* Absolute security is unattainable. The goal is to reduce the risk of re-identification R to a socially and regulatory acceptable threshold ϵ : $R(D', Aux) \leq \epsilon$, where D' is an anonymized set, Aux is knowledge of the attacker [10].
- 3) *Principle of appropriateness and proportionality.* The depth and methods of de-identification are determined by specific, legitimate processing goals. Transformations must be minimally necessary: $Method(d) =$

$\arg \min_{m \in M} Loss(m(d), Goals)$, где $Loss$ - is the utility loss function.

4) *Verifiability principle*. The process must include a mandatory, preferably automated, stage of verifying that the required level of de-identification has been achieved, thereby forming an evidence base.

Metadata management principle. Transformation parameters (keys, generalization methods) must be stored as critical metadata, protected separately from the depersonalized set.

Table 1. Comparative Analysis of De-identification Methods in the Context of the Proposed Principles

Method / Criterion	Compliance with the Principle of Expediency	Verifiability of Results	Preserving Data Usefulness	Metadata Management	Regulatory Clarity
Deletion	high (radical)	trivial (no data available)	zero	not required	high
Complete Pseudonymization	average (identifier replacement)	complex (risk of binding)	high for analysis	critical (replacement keys)	high (but data is still preliminary)
k-anonymity (generalization)	high (parameter k)	formally verifiable	low/medium (loss of accuracy)	generalization parameters required	recognized
Differential Privacy (ϵ)	high (parameter ϵ)	formally verifiable complex	low (noise)	requires noise level	new, but recognized
Deterministic Encryption	low (excessive for analytics)	complex (depends on mode)	zero without decryption	critical (cryptographic keys)	protection, not de-identification
Shuffling (proposed by authors)	high (selective application)	requires attack simulation	very high (format preserved)	critical (parameters changed)	requires justification

The analysis showed that there is no universal best method. The choice should be determined by the context, which confirms the need for a model that integrates different methods into a single manageable process.

Development of a Conceptual Model for the Protection of Personal Data by De-Identification

The model is a representation $\mathcal{M}: D \rightarrow D'$, where D is the initial set of personal data. Input D - Table with M subjects and N attributes.

The classification function $C(d_n) \rightarrow \{ID, QI, SA, NSA\}$ is defined, where ID is an identifier, QI is a quasi-identifier, SA is a confidential attribute, and NSA is a non-confidential attribute.

Processor \mathcal{P} - control loop implementing the function $\mathcal{P}(D, Goals, \epsilon) = D'$. Includes the sequence of steps shown in Fig. 1. Output D' - a set of data for which the condition $\forall R' \in D', \forall Aux \in$

$\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{P}[Reidentify(R', Aux)] < \epsilon$ is satisfied, where \mathcal{A} is a set of assumed attacker models.

Figure 1. Personal data de-identification life cycle in the conceptual model

Explanation of the structure:

Step 1-2: Preparation - data analysis and formation of a target set for processing.

$D = \{R1, R2, \dots, R_m\}$ - multiple entries (subjects) in the database.

$C: D \times A \rightarrow \{ID, QI, SA, NSA\}$ - attribute classification function, where:

- ID - identifying attributes;
- QI - quasi-identifiers;
- SA - sensitive attributes;
- NSA - non-sensitive attributes.

$D_{target} = \{d_i \in Goals \mid C(d_i) \in \{QI, SA, NSA\}\}$ - target set of attributes for processing, where $Goals \subseteq D$ - a subset of records set intended for processing.

Step 3-4: Execution - selection and application of de-identification methods.

$M(d_i) = \arg \min_{m \in M} Loss(m(d_i), Goals)$, selection of a method that minimizes data usability

loss, where \mathcal{M} - a variety of available processing methods.

Step 5-6: Control - verification of results and correction if necessary (closed cycle).

$P[\text{Reidentify}(R', Aux)] < \varepsilon$, the probability of re-identification must be less than the threshold ε , ($\varepsilon > 0$). If risk $R > \varepsilon$, the process returns to Step 3 (selection of methods), and the correction includes analysis of the causes and modification of the parameters.

Step 7-8: Completion - obtaining results and documenting the process.

Metadata is protected separately from depersonalized data D' . All process parameters are saved to ensure accountability and reversibility (where required).

Results

It is advisable to choose the shuffling method (rearranging values between records) in step 3 for QI and SA attributes when it is necessary to:

- preserve accurate values and data format for subsequent calculations;
- ensure reversible de-identification for authorized scenarios;
- avoid the loss of information characteristic of generalization.

Analysis of the impact of implementing a conceptual model for protecting personal data by de-identification in information systems. The implementation of a conceptual de-identification model has a differentiated impact on various aspects of information system functioning. As can be seen from Fig. 2, the greatest positive effect is achieved in the area of reducing regulatory risks (impact coefficient 0.88) and improving the manageability of information security processes (0.85). This is because the model provides a formalized, documented approach to anonymization, which allows organizations to demonstrate compliance with legal requirements (GDPR, No. ZRU-547) and standards.

Evaluation of Implementing a Conceptual Model for Protecting Personal Data by Depersonalization

Figure 2. The impact of implementing a conceptual model for protecting personal data by de-identification

A significant increase in the economic efficiency of information security (0.78) is associated with the possibility of replacing expensive cryptographic solutions with cheaper de-identification methods where permissible, without losing the required level of protection.

At the same time, there is a moderate decrease in development speed (-0.15) and architectural flexibility (-0.25), which is the price to pay for introducing additional control points and procedures. The most significant negative impact is on operational complexity (-0.72), as the model requires the allocation of new roles, regular verification, and metadata repository support. However, this increase in complexity is considered justified and manageable, as it leads to a qualitative improvement in control over the personal data processing process and a reduction in long-term risks. Overall, the balance of positive and negative effects is favorable, confirming the practical value of the proposed conceptual model.

Discussions

The practical validation of the model through the shuffling algorithm case study confirms that a formalized, life cycle-oriented approach is essential for moving de-identification from an intuitive choice to a scientifically defensible, risk-managed decision. By forcing the formal specification of the transformation function with precise constraints and a predefined verification function V with an acceptable risk threshold ε , the de-identification life cycle model provides the rigor necessary to operationalize

principles like accountability and proportionality. The quantitative impact analysis reinforces this value, demonstrating that the model's greatest positive effects are in reducing regulatory risks and improving the manageability of information security processes. This is achieved by transforming compliance into an auditable process and enabling the replacement of expensive cryptographic solutions with proportionate, context-aware de-identification methods, thereby yielding significant economic efficiency.

However, this formalization comes with inherent trade-offs, most notably a substantial increase in operational complexity due to the need for new roles, metadata management, and regular verification. While this complexity and the moderate decreases in development speed and flexibility represent the tangible costs of maturity, they are justified by the qualitative improvement in long-term risk control. The study's limitations - namely the reliance on simulated impact coefficients and the static nature of the adversary model - point directly to future research priorities. Subsequent work must focus on longitudinal, real-world case studies to gather empirical data on these impacts and on developing an adaptive verification function capable of responding to an adversary's evolving knowledge over time.

Conclusion

The proposed conceptual model for depersonalizing personal data represents a formalized life cycle from data classification to result verification. The model based on five synthesized principles that ensure its compliance with regulatory requirements. A comparative analysis of existing de-identification methods conducted, which showed that there is no universal solution and confirmed the need for context-dependent method selection within a single process provided by the model.

The model provides a basis for operator accountability by explicitly highlighting the verification stage and the requirement to document process metadata. In addition, the practical applicability of the model demonstrated by the example of forming a specification of requirements for a data shuffling algorithm, which creates a link

between theoretical design and practical implementation.

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